

Principal Managerial Skills in Implementing School-Based Management: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: This study aimed to describe principals' managerial skills in the development of School-Based Management (SBM). The method used in this study was a literature review. The results and discussion of the study, namely the principal's managerial skills, include; Technical skills (technical abilities), human skills (human relations abilities), and conceptual skills (conceptual abilities), which are implemented in school-based management with components of curriculum management and teaching programs, education staff, student affairs, finance, educational facilities and infrastructure, management of school and community relations, and special services for institutions. The indicators for the success of School-Based Management (SBM) include support from school principals and teachers, sufficient financial resources, clear commitments, responsibilities, skills, and qualifications of school officials, appropriate plans, obligations, and accountability.

KEYWORDS: Principal Managerial, School-Based Management, Success Indicators.

1. BACKGROUND

Humans are formed both individually and collectively through education to best prepare for the future by realizing their potential to possess the religious, spiritual grit, self-control, personality, noble character intelligence, and skills required by themselves, society, nation, and state. A school is a place where people go to learn things like how to read, write, and conduct properly. Schools play a crucial role in a society that is coping with the current issues. The level of objective achievement determines how efficiently schools are run. Then successful schools can utilize the resources they have to achieve the goals that have been set. The principal has the general obligation as the institution's leader to ensure that all of the school's activities are directed toward achieving the set goals and objectives through various well-executed programs that follow the lesson plans. As a manager and leader, the principal thus chooses the route the school should take. They are essentially in charge of running the school as a whole. Their roles are more complex, diversified, and challenging due to the enormous changes in scope, diversity of abilities, and skills needed to run schools. Vision, mission, institutional goals, learning curriculum, financial budgeting, school infrastructure, student services, community connections, and school improvement plans are just a few of the management-related responsibilities of the principal. The issues faced by principals daily, where accountability, challenge, and integrity as leaders and managers are still at stake, are brought up by identifying the competencies needed to operate in this area.

An effective leader is required for a group of individuals since proper management will influence the effectiveness of teamwork. According to Ibay and Pa-alisbo (2020), an efficient manager must have four skills: technical skills, cognitive skills, human skills, and political abilities. The management abilities that may give the proper context for the actions managers and leaders engage in are essential. No manager in today's environment can be successful if they lack management fundamentals. In other words, managers must be knowledgeable about the dynamics of their workplace. As a result, management skills are the foundation for the efficiency and effectiveness of managers' and leaders' performance.

According to Permendiknas No. 13 of 2007, dated April 17, 2017, concerning Standard Criteria for Schools or Madrasahs, school principals must possess five competencies: interpersonal competence, managerial competence, entrepreneurial competence, supervisory competence, and social competence. Managerial competence is the primary key in determining the success of the principal's leadership in maintaining the quality of education. This is defined as the principal's ability to plan and develop human resources to create an effective and efficient learning environment.

A conducive learning environment influences the principal's creativity in applying the managerial skills required to make strategic judgments. The principal's managerial abilities, which are described as a set of abilities in supporting and providing opportunities for teachers to improve their skills through various activities both inside and outside the school, can be used to make these judgments.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW PRINCIPAL MANAGERIAL

According to Khan and Uzair-ul-Hassan (2021), management is the process of getting things done through people to improve organizational performance. Organization and management are interdependent. Without management, no organization can accomplish its aims and objectives. Management, according to Buenavista (2021) is the methodical aspect of running an organization, including establishing objectives and plans, assigning resources, and assessing interim results.

Management is a person's ability or skill to produce something to achieve goals through the activities of others. In order to support the achievement of educational goals themselves, management in education entails the management of all institutional needs in which the system's constituent parts and its subsystems are interrelated and influence. This is reflected in a series of activities or processes of carrying out work by making effective, productive, and efficient use of all resources. Micro-education management, which is directly related to the learning process in schools, the implementation of educational activities, school administration, education staff development, and utilization and maintenance of facilities and infrastructure, is the sole responsibility of the principal in order to accomplish this goal (Sutiara, Ningsih et al. 2021).

A principal as a manager must be ready to manage the school. Readiness in question is related to the managerial ability of the principal as a leader. The administrative capabilities in question are planning (planning), organizing (organizing), implementing (actuating), and controlling (controlling). With these four abilities, it is hoped that every leader will be able to become a driver and enforcer of discipline for his colleagues to show good work productivity.

The three components of managerial ability, according to Hidayat, Subarto et al. (2019), are technical skills (technical abilities), human skills (human relations abilities), and conceptual skills (conceptual abilities). With the exception of human relations skills, managers require varied managerial talents depending on the level of their position. Managers at all levels— lower-level, upper-level, and middle-level managers need human relations expertise (Iskandar 2017).

Expressed a viewpoint on managerial abilities Chasanah (2020), Principals with technical capabilities can carry out specific tasks by leveraging their understanding of tools, methods, and approaches. The application of knowledge regarding classroom management, use of teaching methods, student evaluation techniques, learning program techniques, techniques for managing educational facilities and infrastructure, as well as techniques for directing and fostering teachers in schools are all examples of technical skills. In order to build a culture of mutual trust in each program and inspire teachers to perform better, the administrator must have the human ability to collaborate and interact with the working environment. Realized by providing motivation, opportunities for self-development, appreciation, family attitude, good communication, and delegating tasks. Conceptual ability, namely the principal's ability to decide what happens in organizations such as schools as educational institutions that are listed in the vision, mission, and goals of the school's schedule of short- and long-term activities.

School principals must meet a number of administrative and supervisory capacity standards as part of their principal skills, in addition to explanations of managerial from diverse sources and varied managerial. Adi (2016) suggests that school principals need to possess eleven managerial skills, including the following: (1) the capacity for problem analysis; (2) the capacity for providing considerations, opinions, and decisions; (3) the capacity for managing resources and various activities; (4) the capacity for decision-making; (5) the capacity for leadership; (6) the capacity for sensitivity; (7) the capacity for openmindedness and patience; (8) the capacity for verbal communication; (9) the capacity for written communication; and (10) the capacity for actively participating in the decision.

In the information technology era, it has brought the world into a new generation that was never imagined before. Because of this, profound changes occur in many spheres of life, including education. Based on school-based management, a type of educational reform that grants schools autonomy in managing organizations following their potential, demands, and requirements, this change aims to improve the quality of education for all students. Education quality can be impacted by many factors, including management at the school level.

School Based Management

Usman, Harun et al. (2016) said that efforts to implement programs that have been conceptually determined in order to improve the quality of education still refer to the goals of national education. Arar and Nasra (2020) define SBM as the decentralization of responsibility for decision-making in certain areas at the school level (e.g., learning programs, teaching methods, resources, people, student choice, and accountability). SBM is "a school management model by giving greater authority at the school level to manage their own schools directly (Mistrianingsih, Imron et al. 2015). Indicators in school-based management that can support the performance of school principals include at least the school components that must be adequately managed in the context of SBM, namely "curriculum and teaching programs, education staff, students, finance, educational facilities and infrastructure, management of school relations and the community, as well as the management of special services for educational institutions (Usman, Harun et al. 2016).

According to Suyitno (2021) successful school management in implementing School-Based Management if: 1). The number of students receiving educational services is increasing; 2). Increasingly fun and active teaching and learning activities in all classes throughout the day; 3). Better quality of education services; 4). The class stay rate is decreasing and school productivity is getting better in the sense that the ratio between the number of students enrolling and the number of students graduating is getting bigger; 5). The relevance of education is getting better; 6). The existence of justice in the implementation of education; 7). Increased stakeholder involvement; 8). The better the work climate and culture in schools; 9). Welfare of teachers and school staff improved; 10). Democratization in the implementation of education. Thus, this study aims to find out more about how the managerial skills of principals in the development of school-based management (SBM) are manifested.

3. METHODOLOGY

This research can be categorized as a literature review. This literature review aimed to find a theoretical foundation that can enable fixing an issue. Using the terms "Managerial Principals in SBM Implementation," a Google Scholar search was conducted to find the publication as part of the review process. One hundred fifty research papers linked to the topic were found in the search, which covered articles published from 2015-2022. The requirements for reports to qualify as literature in this study are as follows:

- a. Qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods result from "Managerial Principals in SBM Implementation."
- b. Research from various countries in the world
- c. Research articles are written in English
- d. Dissertation and thesis not included

The steps in the "Managerial Principles in SBM Implementation" Literature Review for each variable are as follows:

Step 1: Formulated the Problem

- Chose a topic that matches your problems and interests
- Problems must be written entirely and accurately

Step 2: Searched the Literature

- Searched for literature relevant to the research
- Got an overview of the research topic
- Research resources were beneficial if they are supported by knowledge related to the studied topic
- Sources must provide an overview/summary related to previous research.

Step 3: Evaluated the data

- Paid attention to the contributions made by articles on the topic
- Paid attention to the data sources needed according to the needs of the topic.
- Data can be quantitative data, qualitative data, or a combination of both

Step 4: Analysis and Interpretation

Step 5: Discussed and summarized the literature

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This section reviews the key research findings from numerous papers the author has read and examines them. Most publications discussed "How Managerial Principals Implement SBM?" The study presented in the articles under evaluation was carried out in

many different nations. Table 1 describes the results of the literature study conducted by the author, and research has been carried out in several schools.

Table 1: Principal Managerial in Implementing SBM

Author & Year	Title	Country	Method	Result
Khalid Arar dan Muhammad Abu Nasra (2020)	Linking schoolbased management and school effectiveness The influence of selfbased management, motivation and effectiveness in the Arab education system in Israel	Arab	Quantitative	This study revealed that school-based management directly or indirectly affects the positive relationship between all management dimensions and school effectiveness.
Arthur Ong Buenavista (2021)	Managerial Leadership and Performance as Fully Mediated by Transformational Leadership through Structural Equation Modeling	Philippines	Quantitative	This study explained that school administrators' managerial and transformational leadership are directly related to their performance.
Siti Nurlaili Chasanah (2020)	<i>Kompetensi Manajerial Kepala Sekolah dalam Meningkatkan Kinerja Guru</i>	Indonesia	Quantitative	This study explained that the managerial application of the principal in the form of technical managerial, humane managerial, and conceptual managerial works well.
Dayat Hidayat, Subarto, Wahyu Novianti (2019)	<i>Kompetensi Manajerial Kepala Sekolah Menengah Kejuruan dalam Peningkatkan Mutu Sekolah di SMK Negeri Se-kota Tangerang</i>	Indonesia	Quantitative	This study demonstrated the principal's managing skills in planning, organizing, directing, and supervising to construct partnerships with organizations that promote managerial and educational development to raise school standards.
Samera Batao Ibay& Mark Anthony Cenas Pa-alisbo (2020)	An Assessment of the Managerial Skills and Professional Development Needs of Private Catholic Secondary School Administrators in Bangkok, Thailand	Thailand	Mixed Method	The knowledge and skills that individual leaders possess and may use to carry out certain management activities or duties are known as managerial skills. When school administrators study and practice their behavior, tactics, and approaches, they will all become better managers.

Jamaluddin Iskandar (2017)	<i>Keterampilan Manajerial Kepala Sekolah</i>	Indonesia	Quantitative	This study explained that the principal always cooperates, coordinates with all parties related to the elements, and always motivates teachers and students.
Najeeb Ullah Khan and Muhammad Uzair-ul-Hassan (2021)	How and to What Extent Managerial Practices of School Heads are Influencing the Morale of Primary School Teachers?	Pakistan	Mixed Method	This study revealed dissatisfaction among teachers about the managerial practices of principals. So the teachers observed that they were under severe mental stress due to the rude and abusive behavior of the principal.
Siti Mistrianingsih, Ali Imron dan Ahmad Nurabadi (2015)	<i>Peran Kepala Sekolah dalam Implemetasi Manajemen Berbasis Sekolah</i>	Indonesia	Qualitative	The seven SBM pillars are put into practice by principals and are evaluated by EDS, SOPs, and parental surveys. SBM stands for school-based management. Parents were active in school, and students sat in one room while communicating with numerous parties.
Yulia Rachmawati, Suyatno, Achadi Budi Santosa (2020)	Principal's Managerial Competence in Actualizing a Creative School	Indonesia	Qualitative	The principal's managerial competence consists of conceptual, technical, and interpersonal competencies to realize a creative school. Principals apply six ways: establish a vision and mission, implement innovative programs, implement responsive management, build productive culture, improve the quality of human resources, and build cooperation.
Aditia Sutiara, Ines Widiya Ningsih,	<i>Manajerial Kepala Sekolah Dalam</i>	Indonesia	Qualitative	Principals can improve education quality, including educators, managers, administrators, supervisors, leaders, innovators, and motivators. His role is
Muhamad, Khozinul Huda Rokman Hidayat (2021)	<i>Meningkatkan Mutu Pendidik Di Sdn 4 Margadadi</i>			very complex, so the principal must monitor and evaluate the vision, mission and programs implemented
Suyitno (2021)	<i>Pengaruh Keterampilan Manajerial Kepala Sekolah Dan Peran Komite Terhadap Efektivitas Manajemen Berbasis Sekolah</i>	Indonesia	Quantitative	This study explained that the managerial skills of the principal and the committee's role together have an effect of being applied optimally to increase the effectiveness or success of implementing school-based management.

Aswanita Usman, Cut Zahri Harun, Murniati (2016)	<i>Implementasi Manajemen Berbasis Sekolah pada SMA 5 Bandar Aceh</i>	Indonesia	Qualitative	School-Based Management is implemented in curriculum management, student management, personnel, finance, and public relations.
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The implementation of school-based management has been the subject of research studies in many different nations. As seen in Table 1 above, academic institutions have researched managerial principles in SBM implementation. Based on the findings of a literature review of the sources consulted, the analysis demonstrates that management is a more extensive activity than managerial since it encompasses actions like planning, organizing, coordinating, leading, and supervising. The principal's role as a manager, planner, and supervisor of the school community's activities is crucial to a school's success. A school's development is linked to the principal's managerial abilities (Trimono 2019). Since the significant recommendations for teachers to carry out the teaching and learning process depends on the principal or the principal's policy and activities, the principal's administrative abilities are crucial to the success of educational circumstances (Anjani and Dafit 2021). joint decision-making. (6) School-Based Management can improve student achievement due to increased efficiency in the use of resources and personnel, increased teacher professionalism, implementation of curriculum reform, and increased community involvement in education (Rosmalah 2016).

5. CONCLUSION

This study focused on a review of the literature from earlier studies to analyze how the principal's managerial management is controlled by using SBM. Most of the review's findings indicated that it is challenging to find literature on adopting SBM and principal managerial practices. Because the major recommendations for teachers to carry out the teaching and learning process depend on the principal or the principal's policies and the actions of the principal, the principal's administrative abilities are highly significant in the success of educational circumstances. Therefore, the management expertise that the principal plays and owns is essential to the growth and advancement of a school.

In conclusion, the authors of this paper believe that the managerial study of principals in SBM implementation is a helpful step for advancing principals' managerial information in SBM implementation. Having such an advanced understanding will also make it possible to develop the managerial abilities of principals and the implementation of SBM that is easier to understand.

REFERENCES

1. Adi, A. (2016). "Implementasi kompetensi manajerial kepala sekolah kecamatan Kuala Kampar Kabupaten Pelalawan Propinsi Riau." *Jurnal Akuntabilitas Manajemen Pendidikan* 4(1): 1-16.
2. Anjani, N. F. and F. Dafit (2021). "Peran Manajerial Kepala Sekolah dalam Meningkatkan Mutu Pendidikan." *MIMBAR PGSD Undiksha* 9(3).
3. Arar, K. and M. A. Nasra (2020). "Linking school-based management and school effectiveness: The influence of selfbased management, motivation and effectiveness in the Arab education system in Israel." *Educational Management Administration & Leadership* 48(1): 186-204.
4. Buenavista, A. O. (2021). "Managerial Leadership and Performance as Fully Mediated by Transformational Leadership through Structural Equation Modeling."
5. Chasanah, S. N. (2020). "KOMPETENSI MANAGERIAL KEPALA SEKOLAH DALAM MENINGKATKAN KINERJA GURU DI SMP NEGERI 9 PURWOREJO." *Ar-Rihlah: Jurnal Inovasi Pengembangan Pendidikan Islam* 5(1): 84-103.
6. Hidayat, D., et al. (2019). "Kompetensi Manajerial Kepala Sekolah Menengah Kejuruan Dalam Peningkatan Mutu Sekolah Di Smk Negeri Se-Kota Tangerang Selatan." *Inovasi* 6(2): 80-99.
7. Ibay, S. B. and M. A. C. Pa-alisbo (2020). "An Assessment of the Managerial Skills and Professional Development Needs of Private Catholic Secondary School Administrators in Bangkok, Thailand." *World Journal of Education* 10(1): 149-163.
8. Iskandar, J. (2017). "Keterampilan Manajerial Kepala Sekolah." *Idaarah: Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan* 1(1).

9. Khan, N. U. and M. Uzair-ul-Hassan (2021). "How and to What Extent Managerial Practices of School Heads are Influencing the Morale of Primary School Teachers?" Bulletin of Education and Research 43(2): 83-96.
10. Mistrianingsih, S., et al. (2015). "Peran kepala sekolah dalam implementasi manajemen berbasis sekolah." Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan 24(5): 367-375.
11. Rosmalah, R. (2016). "Hakikat Implementasi Manajemen Berbasis Sekolah." Jurnal Publikasi Pendidikan 6(1): 64-76. 12. Sutiara, A., et al. (2021). "Manajerial Kepala Sekolah Dalam Meningkatkan Mutu Pendidik Di SDN 4."
12. Suyitno, S. (2021). "Pengaruh Keterampilan Manajerial Kepala Sekolah Dan Peran Komite Terhadap Efektivitas Manajemen Berbasis Sekolah." Jurnal Basicedu 5(3): 1564-1576.
13. Trimono, T. (2019). "Hubungan Kompetensi Manajerial Kepala Sekolah dengan Kinerja." Al-Mutharahah: Jurnal Penelitian Dan Kajian Sosial Keagamaan 16(1): 207-229.
14. Usman, A., et al. (2016). "Implementasi Manajemen Berbasis Sekolah Pada SMA Negeri 5 Banda Aceh." Jurnal Administrasi Pendidikan: Program Pascasarjana Unsyiah 4(1).

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